

Electronic Spectra of Carbazole Derivatives

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The shift in the longest wavelength absorption band of substituted carbazole is theoretically calculated. The calculation shows fair agreement with the experimentally determined values.

Substituted carbazoles are of interest to chemists because of their analogous properties to some naturally occurring plant degraded products. The longest wavelength electronic spectra of substituted carbazoles may be bathochromic or hypsochromic depending upon the position and nature of the substituents. This diagnostic behaviour of UV spectra has of late been used in the structural studies of some natural products. As the UV—spectra of carbazole arises from the transition between π —electronic energy levels of the conjugated system, it is possible to make approximate theoretical calculation of the extent and direction of spectral shift in carbazole with the position of the substituent in the carbazole nucleus. In the present paper are reported the result of theoretical calculations of the spectra of substituted carbazoles especially the methyl derivatives. Simple Huckel methods have been used in conjunction with Longuet-Higgins and Sowden's perturbation method¹. The Huckel molecular orbitals for parent carbazole is given in the appendix.

It is an accepted fact that the methyl group brings about a change in the spectra due to its inductive and hyperconjugative effect.

Inductive effect :

The net change in transition energy due to the inductive effect is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\Delta\epsilon_{ab})_{induc} &= (\epsilon_{b'} - \epsilon_{a'}) - (\epsilon_b - \epsilon_a) \\
 &= (C_{br}^2 - C_{ar}^2) \delta \alpha_r + \left(\sum_{j \neq b} \frac{C_{br}^2 C_{jr}^2}{\epsilon_b - \epsilon_j} - \sum_{j \neq a} \frac{C_{ar}^2 C_{jr}^2}{\epsilon_a - \epsilon_j} \right) (\delta \alpha_r)^2 \quad \dots (1)
 \end{aligned}$$

where a and b refer to the highest filled and the lowest empty molecular orbitals of carbazole respectively, the primed quantities refer to substituted carbazoles and the unprimed to carbazole itself. C_{jr} refers to atomic orbital coefficient of the r^{th} carbon in the j^{th} molecular orbital. Simple Huckel calculation was done for carbazole molecule itself, Coulomb integral for nitrogen being taken as $(\alpha_n + 1.5\beta)$, (α_n being the Coulomb integral for aromatic carbon), all resonance integrals being set equal to $-\beta = \beta_{n-c}$.

Hyperconjugative effect:

If β_{rs} is the resonance integral of the bond formed between the r^{th} carbon atom of carbazole and s^{th} carbon atom of the substituent then Longuet-Higgins and Sowden

1. Longuet-Higgins and Sowden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1404.

showed that the energy change due to hyperconjugative effect can be written as

$$(\Delta \epsilon_{ab})_{\text{hypercon}} = \beta_{rs}^2 \left(\frac{C_{br}^a C_{ks}^a}{\sum_{a \neq b} \epsilon_b - \epsilon_k} - \frac{C_{ar}^a C_{ks}^a}{\sum_{a \neq s} \epsilon_a - \epsilon_k} \right) \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

A conjugating methyl group was considered as $-\text{C}\equiv\text{H}_3$ with the following Coulomb and resonance parameters $\alpha_{\text{om}} = \alpha_{\text{o}} - 0.1 \beta$, $\beta_{\text{ms}} = 2.5 \beta$, $\alpha_{\text{ms}} = \alpha_{\text{o}} - 0.5 \beta$ and $\beta_{\text{rs}} = 0.7 \beta$. When both R and S are conjugated system the above equation is applicable.

If instead one of the reacting species is a single atom or a group in which the atom S is attached to substituents only by the σ -bonds the equation is somewhat simplified. If the Coulomb term of the atom S is α and if no energy level of R coincides with α the approximate energies of RS can be simplified and so $(\Delta \epsilon_{ab})_{\text{hypercon}}$ can be written as

$$(\Delta \epsilon_{ab})_{\text{hypercon}} = (\beta_{rs})^2 \left(\frac{C_{br}^a}{\epsilon_b - \alpha} - \frac{C_{ar}^a}{\epsilon_a - \alpha} \right) \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

The resultant is calculated by mere addition of the two separate effects, i.e.

$$(\Delta \epsilon_{ab})_{\text{total}} = (\Delta \epsilon_{ab})_{\text{induc}} + (\Delta \epsilon_{ab})_{\text{hypercon}} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

$\Delta \lambda$ is the energy difference converted into wavelength ($\text{m}\mu$) calculated by taking $\beta = -23,000 \text{ Cm}^{-1}$. The $(\Delta \epsilon_{ab})_{\text{total}}$ and the shift in terms of $\Delta \lambda$ are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Calculated and experimental spectral shift in methyl carbazoles

$$(\epsilon_b - \epsilon_a) = -1.412 \beta$$

Methylcarbazole	$(\Delta \epsilon_{ab})_{\text{induc}}$	$(\Delta \epsilon_{ab})_{\text{hypercon}}$	$(\Delta \epsilon_{ab})_{\text{total}}$	$(\Delta \lambda)_{\text{calc. m}\mu}$	$(\Delta \lambda)_{\text{obs. m}\mu}$
3-methylcarbazole	+0.002558 β	+0.01778 β	+0.020338 β	4	no change
4-methylcarbazole	-0.009614 β	+0.005782 β	-0.003832 β	-1	-2
5-methylcarbazole	+0.006556 β	+0.008100 β	+0.014656 β	3	8
6-methylcarbazole	+0.009438 β	+0.012619 β	+0.022057 β	5	no data

TABLE II

Spectral shift in methoxy and aminocarbazoles in terms of $\delta \alpha$ and $\delta \beta$

3-substituted carbazole	-0.0074 ($\delta \alpha$)	+0.25470 ($\delta \alpha$) ²	+0.25679 ($\beta_{\text{rs}})$ ²
4-substituted carbazole	+0.1030 ($\delta \alpha$)	+0.09191 ($\delta \alpha$) ²	-0.00630 ($\beta_{\text{rs}})$ ²
5-substituted carbazole	-0.0582 ($\delta \alpha$)	+0.05965 ($\delta \alpha$) ²	+0.16461 ($\beta_{\text{rs}})$ ²
6-substituted carbazole	-0.0705 ($\delta \alpha$)	+0.36453 ($\delta \alpha$) ²	+0.23912 ($\beta_{\text{rs}})$ ²

DISCUSSION

The existing data for methyl substituted carbazolo^a when compared to the calculated spectral shift, fairly good agreement is obtained. For 4-methyl group the calculated spectral shift is hypsochromic as is verified by experimental result whereas in 3-methyl, 5-methyl and 6-methyl substituted carbazole the calculated spectral shift is bathochromic. Calculations can also be made with other substituents like methoxy and amino group, taking into considerations inductive and mesomeric effect. As no experimental data are available for these systems, the results are given in terms of $\delta\alpha$ and $\delta\beta$ for these systems in the Table II. It may be mentioned that the experimental data on methoxy carbazoles are incomplete as the reported band systems do not follow f-sum rule. The longest wavelength shifts in different dimethyl carbazoles as predicted from theoretical considerations are given in Table III.

TABLE III
Predicted spectral shift in dimethyl carbazoles.

Carbazoles	$(\Delta\epsilon_{ab})$ induc.	(Δ_{ab}) hypercon	(Δ_{ab}) total	$(\Delta\lambda)_{m\mu}$
(3, 3')	+0.005116 β	+0.03556 β	0.040676 β	9
(4, 4')	-0.019228 β	+0.011564 β	0.007664 β	- 2
(5, 5')	+0.013112 β	-0.016200 β	0.029312 β	6
(6, 6')	+0.018876 β	+0.025238 β	0.044114 β	10
(3, 4)	-0.007056 β	+0.023562 β	+0.016506 β	4
(3, 5)	+0.009114 β	+0.025880 β	+0.034994 β	8
(3, 6)	+0.011996 β	+0.030999 β	+0.042995 β	9
(4, 5)	-0.003058 β	+0.019882 β	+0.010824 β	2
(4, 6)	-0.000176 β	+0.018401 β	+0.018225 β	4
(5, 6)	+0.015994 β	+0.020719 β	+0.036713 β	4

APPENDIX

Atomic orbital coefficients of carbazoles are tabulated as below: The y direction is the straight line through the N atom and bisecting the bond connecting the 7th and 8th carbon atom. The numbering of the atoms in the carbazole molecule are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 : Molecular geometry of carbazole.

This procedure is followed for the theoretical calculation which do not conform the usual convention of organic chemistry.

Energy level	Symmetry	G ₍₁₎	G ₍₂₎	G ₍₃₎	G ₍₄₎	G ₍₅₎	G ₍₆₎	G ₍₇₎
E ₀ +2.778 β	Sy	0.6149	0.3929	0.1749	0.09298	0.08333	+0.1385	+0.3017
E ₀ +1.8913 β	Ay	0	0.2896	0.3473	0.3672	0.3473	0.2896	0.2004
E ₀ +1.8012 β	Sy	0.4972	0.0749	-0.0697	-0.2003	-0.2912	-0.3241	-0.2927
E ₀ +1.9173 β	Sy	0.0569	-0.0052	0.3185	0.4248	0.2410	-0.1073	-0.3823
E ₀ + β	Ay	0	0.3536	0.3536	0	-0.3536	-0.3536	0
E ₀ +0.705 β	Ay	0	0.2991	-0.1430	-0.3980	-0.1403	0.2991	0.3512
E ₀ +0.627 β	Sy	0.3667	-0.1601	-0.4002	-0.1747	0.2906	0.3569	-0.0669
E ₀ -0.785 β	Sy	0.0887	-0.0570	-0.3930	-0.3654	-0.1618	-0.2385	0.3490
E ₀ - β	Ay	0	0.3536	-0.3536	0	-0.3536	-0.3536	0
E ₀ -1.232 β	Sy	0.2834	-0.3871	0.1460	0.2073	-0.4013	0.2871	0.0476
E ₀ -1.319 β	Ay	0	0.0175	0.0885	-0.1342	0.1053	0.0175	0.1115
E ₀ -2.0065 β	Sy	0.2870	-0.5031	0.4515	-0.4027	0.3566	0.3128	0.2711
E ₀ -2.2773 β	Ay	0	0.2922	-0.2088	0.1834	-0.2088	+0.2921	-0.4566

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